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CAREER DEVELOPMENT AND ORGANISATIONAL PERFORMANCE IN THE NIGERIAN BANKING INDUSTRY: A STUDY OF PALMERA MICROFINANCE BANK LTD, UROMI, EDO STATE

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this study is to examine the relationship between career development and employee job satisfaction and the concomitant organisational performance in the Nigerian Microfinance Banks using Palmera Micro-Finance Bank Ltd, Uromi as a case study. The study adopts the survey research design method using the structured questionnaire strategy. Three factors were tested using the Spearman's Correlation statistical analysis aided with the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 25 at 5% level of significance. A total population/sample size of 58 staff members of the Bank was purposively selected. The results of the study indicate that there is a high positive relationship between career counselling, employee training, and career mentoring with employee's job satisfaction respectively; and that there is a significant positive relationship between employee's job satisfaction and organisational performance. It was recommended, among others, that for Palmera Micro-Finance Bank Ltd, Uromi to achieve maximum productivity, it must design and implement an effectively pragmatic employee career development programmes that can meet its employees' expected needs.

KEYWORDS

Career Development, Career, Employee Satisfaction, Organisational Performance

Introduction

Today, there is intense business competition around the world especially since the emergence of the internet and globalisation. Such competition has not only adversely affected profit earnings of organisations like Microfinance Banks, it has also increased employee turnover and decreased the level of employee retention. To stem such ugly experiences, there is the need for banks, particularly Microfinance Banks, to evolve policies that can bring about employee satisfaction and commitment. Until an organisation rewards and provides certain levels of opportunities to its employees that can lead to their career progression, it is usually difficult to procure one percent employees commitment, especially the highly skilled ones. Thus, organisations should have strategic policies which include career counselling and goals setting, staff orientation, on/off-the-job training, short courses, professional courses, and many more (Anekwe et al., 2020) that are tailored towards building and developing employee career.

With appropriate and adequate career development/management programmes, employees can understand what abilities and capabilities they need to possess to be able to fulfil their career goals. Planning an employee career development is as important to the individual employee as it is to the organisation itself. To plan an employee career development cannot be done in isolation of the needs of the employee as much as that of the organisation. This is because career development involves identifying the minimum competency levels required of an employee to perform a particular task (Anekwe et al., 2020) in the organisation; hence, individual employee's needs cannot be satisfied without actually satisfying the organisation's needs (Lingham, 2000). Therefore, the human resource (employees) of any organisation is crucial in the achievement of organisational success or failure (Anekwe et al., 2020) and competitiveness. To this end, the development and proper management of employee career in any organisation requires thorough study and analysis.

There are procedures for achieving career development (Anekwe et al., 2020). Such procedures may include career counselling, personal development planning, training and management development, mentoring, etc. (Çiğdem& Belgin, 2014). Career development may involve providing complementary learning on the job, and acquiring benefits from experienced mentors for a particular skill. Mentors in this case provide advice to their allocated mentees regarding administrative and technical problems that people meet, and necessary knowledge and skills to overcome those problems (Sword, 2021). Career development involves continuously learning new things, applying new knowledge and taking advantage of opportunities. It is also about risk taking in order to make the organisation more effective and productive, and allows the individual employee achieve personal and organisational goals (Sobia et al., 2013). The purpose of career development is to enhance employees' current performance, take advantage of future jobs and to fulfil their career goals (Anekwe et al., 2020). Effective career development is based on a three tripod – the employee, the managers and the organisation itself. This is because it is the employee who decides what his/her career objective and outcome should be while the responsibility of the manager is to identify the right knowledge, skills and abilities required to perform a particular job/task in an organisation, and then train the employees according to the needs of the organisation by helping to identify both the short and long term goals of the organisation (Çiğdem& Belgin, 2014; Sobia et al., 2013). Organisations also provide employees time, benefits and funds as they may require through supporting them for their goals by using the knowledge, skills and abilities of each of the individual employees to achieve organisational goals (Anekwe et al., 2020; Duggan, 2011; Nameoff, 2009).

Generally, Banks have some underpinning tenets such as providing quality services that can yield the best competitive results within the industry. The general success (profitability) of Banks, just like other organisations, depend among other things, on their dedicated and skilful employees, as well as their level of training, communication skills and employees' rotation speed (Wallace et al., 2013). This explains why Banks usually make efforts to attract customer-oriented employees, who are able to meet the needs of their clients (Iuga, 2014). Generally, banks and their employees need to remain committed to each other especially during periods of economic uncertainty and customer frustration as witnessed during the CoronaVirus of 2019 (COVID-19) pandemic (Anekwe et al., 2020).

However, in this study, our focus is on the Microfinance banking subsector of the banking industry. The importance of personal development and career mentoring cannot be overemphasised given that such will usually improve the employees value to the organisation on the one hand and the overall organisational performance on the other (Iuga, 2014). Therefore, following several research findings (see for example: Anekwe et al., 2020; Iuga, 2014; Çiğdem& Belgin, 2014; Sobia et al., 2013), career development/management has been associated with employee satisfaction and organisational performance. However, it has been observed that there is a relatively poor service delivery and low productivity in Microfinance Banks in Nigeria especially in rural communities. This has been attributed to lack of proper career development/management programmes for employees by Microfinance Banks in comparison with their larger commercial/development counterparts. Several Microfinance Banks in Nigeria are said to no longer engage in employee mentoring and self-development (Sobia et al., 2013) despite the acknowledgement that formal mentoring programmes enhance female mentees' career development as well as the major high street Banks (Iuga, 2014; Gillian, 2009). As a result, Microfinance Bank employees are consequently beginning to lack the necessary skills and knowledge to deliver quality services, improve individual performance and ensure that their organisations maintain competitive advantage over rivals (Anekwe et al., 2020). Thus, the poor service delivery and the decrease in employee performance have spirally led to the decline in customer satisfaction. Indeed, Microfinance Banks managers sometimes get confused when their highly-rated employees under-perform and at another bewildered when others resign and leave the organisation. Sometimes, management fail to understand why some employees are not committed to their jobs even though they have proactively implemented fair compensation policies and human resource (HR) practices to motivate them (Agboola et al., 2020; Hassan, 2016).

Although there is yet no consensus on the direction of relationship between career development and employee performance and satisfaction, majority of research findings is skewed towards positive relationship. For instance, while Hassan (2016) found that human resource practices such as career planning, training, and employee involvement have a positive impact on employee's performance, Rawashdeh and Al-Adwan (2012), on the contrary, found that staff training and development negatively impact firm's performance. This is the crux of this study. Therefore, the main objective of this study is to determine the relationship between career development and organisational performance in the banking industry in Nigeria using thePalmera Microfinance Bank limited, Uromias a case study. To completely capture the essence of the main object, the following are the specific objectives:

1. To investigate the impact of career development on organisational performance;
2. To examine the relationship between career development and employee satisfaction;

3. To examine the relationship between employee job satisfaction and organisational performance

In this study, career development is characterised as career counselling, employee training programmes, and employee career mentoring. In other words, career counselling, employee training programmes and employee career mentoring are used as proxies for career development.

Palmera Microfinance Bank Limited, Uromi, Edo State

Palmera Microfinance Bank limited was founded on 14th April 1992 and located at Uromi in Esan North East local government area of Edo Central Senatorial zone of Edo State as a private company with a company number 194295. It was formerly known as "Uromi Microfinance Bank limited". It is limited by shares and established to carry on general financial and banking business and in particular to lend or advance money and to give credit upon the security of real or personal property of every description except insurance and pension funding. As at today, the bank has staff strength of 58 members made up of 11 senior and 47 junior. On April 14, 2022, Palmera turned 30 years in micro-financial operations.

Literature Review

The Conceptual Framework

Career Development

Although the term career has several meanings, however, there is some commonality among the various definitions as seen during the literature review. One of such commonalities is that career describes a series of positions occupied by an individual throughout his or her life time (Robbins & Coulter, 2009). Which means that career is a profession (such as saying that a person has chosen a career in teaching). It is a lifelong sequence of jobs meaning that it is a sequence of positions that a person has held over a life time or still holds. Therefore, career denotes a stable employment within a profession.

According to Çiğdem and Belgin (2014), career is the constant progress, experience and skills acquisition of a person in a specific field of endeavour. The career of an individual does not refer only to the jobs the individual has presently or does, but it also includes his/her training for meeting the job expectation, the goal, emotion, and the desires related to the job role. An individual is said to have a career if s/he enjoys personal progression in the workplace as s/he exhibits his/her knowledge, skill, and quality, and the desire to work (Çiğdem & Belgin, 2014; Adıgüzel, 2009; Yılmaz, 2006; Phifer, 2003). However, career is said to be planned by an individual when there is a systematic effort by that individual to identify the coherence and incoherence between what s/he wants to do and what s/he has done after evaluating his/her educational background whether in the past, in the present and with regard to his/her future intentions given the person's trainings, personal traits, skills, experiences, choices and expectations (Geylan et al., 2013; Aytaç, 2005).

Career development, from the perspective of the individual, is usually seen as the process of learning, managing life, and working over one's lifespan (Dawn, 2020). It is a vital element of an individual lifecycle as it assists in the navigation of one's way through education and training into employment and fulfilling work life. When viewed from the perspective of organisations, career development is the efforts made by organisations in career development programmes to aid employees' career path so as to improve organisational commitment and performance (Kakui, 2016;

Çiğdem& Belgin, 2014). Such career development programmes help to develop employee performance, increase the managers' improvement, reveal corporate culture for employees (salespeople), strengthen organisational principal values, help salespeople in career improvement, and offer an extra benefit to employees (Ko, 2012). This will enable the employee make progress in performing their organisational tasks. It also helps to remove all obstacles against the progress of the workers.

Ideally, workers choose and remain in organisations that support their career interests as they do for organisations that have career development programmes of their interest (Çalık&Ereş, 2006). For example, if an organisation has an effective career development programme that meets the employees' personal expectations, the employees will usually want to stay with the organisation. Sometimes, similar or equal value of job satisfaction is acknowledged by both employee and his employer for a task achieved. This coincidental homogeneity in job satisfaction usually leads to increasing satisfaction for both the organisation and employees. Conversely, disparity between personal and organisational goals leads to increasing dissatisfaction for both the organisation and employees (Karakurum, 2005). Therefore, career development should be of best interest to both the worker and his/her employer.

Employee Counselling: Counselling connotes the process of helping to explore and possibly resolve problems that could impact performance. Therefore, counselling an employee in an organisation involves a situation in which an employee (counselee) is offered advice, direction, and suggestions through different means by a counsellor in order to improve the counselee's physical and mental conditions needed to solve a prevailing problem. In employee counselling the counsellor and counselee usually work together to clearly define the problem such that the counselee is able to develop a self-determined solution. Employee counselling is normally provided by a more senior employee such as supervisors, managers or consultants depending on the organisation's policy choice with the intent to solving existing problems. Thus, an individual (counselee) uses the services of a counsellor to deal with a specific problem. Indeed, counselling tend to be more focused on emotions and feelings than performance.

Employee Mentoring: Mentoring can be defined as the general guidance or advice regarding life or career. In other words, mentoring is a process in which a employee (mentee) undergoes a training system under a senior or more experienced person (the mentor) who is assigned to act as an advisor, counsellor, or guide to the mentee. Mentoring can be formal or informal. It is informal when it takes place spontaneously between senior and more junior employees in the course of performing their separate functions. However, it is said to be formal when it occurs through a formally articulated programme with an established structure. In mentoring, the mentor is responsible for providing support to, and feedback on, the person in his or her charge. Thus, mentoring is the process of sharing the mentor's knowledge and experience with a mentee. In general, mentoring covers a range of issues that helps people progress within a specific field or organisation. Usually, when an individual seeks a mentor, it is expected that that individual (potential mentee) will look for a role model who s/he can relate to on a personal level as well as someone who is well-respected within their area. Specifically, when we talk about organisational mentoring we are looking at a process that provides guidance and clear understanding of how an organisation achieves its vision and mission statements to the junior employee.

Employee Training: Generally speaking, training means teaching someone what to do and how to do it. In this vein, we can then define employee training as a planned set of activities by organisations for imparting knowledge to employees which can lead to a growth in job skills that can eventually lead to organisational growth. It's the process by which someone learns a new skill or piece of knowledge which may include technical, vocational, or management skills. Training leads to empowering someone with the tools to do a job, thereby moving that person from conscious incompetence to conscious competence (BasuMallick, 2020). Employee training is more production-centric and aimed at problem-solving. Usually, employee training is a short-term endeavour which focuses primarily on improving the production capacity of organisations including its products or services. It is giving someone the tools to do a job, thereby moving that person from conscious incompetence to conscious competence. At the end of a training session the learner may be able to do the job, but not necessarily achieving the required standard all of the time. Training can be formal (e.g. training courses) or informal (e.g. on-the-job instruction).

Career Development Model

Figure 1 presents the conceptual framework of this study. The framework depicts the relationship between three factors found during literature review (as cumulative proxy for career development) and employee job satisfaction and organisational performance. It symbolically illustrates the nexus between career development and organisational performance. The figure graphically illustrates our hypotheses that career counselling, employee training, and career mentoring – proxies for career development – lead to employee job satisfaction as well as organisational performance.

From Figure 1, it is clear that career development structure is a long term complex process which both the organisation and individual need to understand and appreciate. Often time, career development is seen as an organisational level initiative in which organisations are expected to set up mechanisms, processes, structures and systems that can foster career development initiatives for its employees (Herr, 2001).

Figure 1: Career Development and Organisational Performance Model

Source: Adapted with modification from Ryan, T.A. (1973). A conceptual model of career development. *Educational Technology*, 13(6), 28-38. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/44420391> with substantial modifications

Nonetheless, in recent years, this perception is beginning to gradually change as individuals have been seen to develop their own initiatives to not only pursue their careers but also take actions to shape, mould and develop them in order to receive maximum advantage from their efforts.

Notwithstanding such an individual initiatives, Appelbaum et al. (2002) argue that organisations can still assist such individual level initiatives by providing career planning tools or workshops through vocational counselling, or by using workbooks or career resource centres to guide employees to conduct self assessment, analyse and evaluate their career options and preference, write down their development objectives and prepare the implementation plan.

Employee Job Satisfaction

Organisations that invest in career management and development are more likely to improve employee's job satisfaction (Lee 2000). Job satisfaction has been the most widely researched job attitude and also among the most extensively researched subjects in Industrial/Organisational Psychology (Judge & Church, 2000). Therefore, this study will find it an easy subject to discuss using the avalanche of definitions predating this present effort.

Several authors have described job satisfaction as a state-of-the-mind phenomenon. Along this school of thought are Gregson (1987) who defines job satisfaction as the positive emotional state resulting from the individual appraisal of one's job or experience. Other notable scholars are Chay and Bruvold (2003) who see job satisfaction as an individual's affective response to specific aspects of the job. Also, Appelbaum et al. (2002) described job satisfaction as a pleasurable feeling that results from the perception that one's job allows for the fulfilment of one's important job values.

Another school of thought sees job satisfaction as a form of attitude towards work related conditions, facets or aspects (Bernstein & Nash, 2008). Jepsen and Sheu (2003) observe that such an attitude, either in the form of liking, or disliking a job, is a universal and an essential aspect of career development. Clearly, theorists and practitioners seem to accept the assumption that nearly everybody seeks satisfaction in his or her work (Jepsen & Sheu, 2003). According to the duo, if a person becomes engaged in work that matches his occupational choices, he is likely to experience job satisfaction.

Job satisfaction can be measured in various ways. For example, you can use "Overall Job Satisfaction" or "Job Descriptive Index (JDI)", or "Global Job Satisfaction", or "Job Satisfaction Relative to Expectations", etc. with each providing measures for different aspects of satisfaction. However, the measurement proposal presented by Fields (2002) in which he outlined specific types of employee satisfaction measures is intended to describe an employee's satisfaction with one or more aspects of their job. These aspects of their jobs include: 1. Employee Satisfaction with Influence and Ownership; 2. Satisfaction with Work Schedule Flexibility; and 3. Satisfaction with Supervisor.

Organisational Performance

Organisational performance connotes a comparative analysis or an inventory taking to determine the actual output of an organisation measured against its intended outputs in terms of its goals and objectives. Organisational performance is the achievement or fulfilment of an organisational goals and objectives at the end of a time period. Organisational performance involves the achievement of three basic indices by an organisation. The indices are shareholder's value, financial performance and market performance. To determine whether an organisation has performed over a period of time, two questions are asked. 1. is the firm or organisation doing as well as it had planned or set out to achieve? 2. Is it doing as well as it said it would? If the answers to the two questions are in the affirmative, then the firm can be said to have performed. Several methods are used to compute performance. However, while some are quantitative in nature, others are non-quantitative (nominal)

Theoretical Review

This study is underpinned by two generic career theories which have been applied by past researchers (see for example: Flanigan, 2011; Nauta, 2010; Hall & Brassard, 2008; Potoczniak et al., 2007). The theories are the **Trait and Factor Theory** (Parsons, 1909) and **Ego Identity Theory** (Tiedeman & O'hara, 1963). Parsons (1909) who is known as the "*father of vocational guidance*" argued that it is possible to measure both individual talents and the attributes required to perform a particular job. It further assumes that people may be matched to an occupation that's a good fit. Thus, the intention of the theory is essentially to match people and occupations in respect of their abilities, interests, intelligence, attitude and aptitude (Giobbi, 2018). The theory also asserts that the individual's needs and values can only be fully realised when they are matched with those jobs which are relevant to such needs and values. Basically, the theory enunciates four assumptions professing that if an individual's personality is carefully observed; better prediction can be made about his career behaviour.

Given the underlying theory, it is clear that any organisation that wants to achieve result must factor-in the implications of these two theories while strategizing on the career development policies and programmes for its employees.

Empirical Review and Hypotheses Development

Career Development and Organisational Performance

Umar and Akram (2011) analysed the relationship between the impact of some career development variables (supervisor support, career development, work environment and work life balance) on employee job satisfaction in Business Process Outsourcing (BPO) industry in Pakistan. The result revealed that career development among other variables has high positive impact on employee satisfaction in BPOs in Pakistanis industry. In the same vein, Chen et al. (2004) surveyed the capability of career development programmes in responding to career needs at different levels of career development stages and its influence on job satisfaction, professional development and productivity among Research & Development (R&D) personnel. One of the major findings of the study was that career development programmes positively influence job satisfaction, professional development and productivity.

In specific terms, several studies have sort to determine the impact of some specific career development variables on employee job satisfaction. For example, Shelton (2001) conducted research to analyse the impact of employee development programmes on employee retention and job satisfaction with regard to business success. The study found that training and development increase employee satisfaction and tend to booster the interest of employees to want to remain in the organisation. The study also found that there is a significant positive relationship between training perception and employee commitment meaning that the availability of training and development programmes tend to demonstrate organisations' care for their employees; having giving them the opportunity to learn and develop their career goals (Ashar et al. (2013).

Walia and Bajaj (2012) examined the impact of Human Resource(HR) practices on employee satisfaction among the employees of the branches of ICIC Bank, AXIS Bank and HDFC Bank in the Haryana state. It was concluded that retention is very important and could be done through the employee job satisfaction, better policies of the organisation like, work life balance, supervisor support (career mentoring and counselling), proper incentives, benefit policies, good working conditions and opportunities to providing them training and development to enhance their skills. It

was also found that career development and working environment show the highest relationship with employee job satisfaction. The implication is that employees would naturally want to work at an organisation where they can get support from their peers and colleagues in the course of developing their careers.

Shani and Divyapriya (2013) conducted a study on the relationship between knowledge management and career development among IT professionals. The ideas were that, to meet the new challenges and retaining good employees, organisations should have to develop the knowledge management practices to enhance awareness regarding career development, sharing knowledge regarding career plans, career counselling, from the very beginning of their careers. It was found that lack of training and knowledge-sharing is the main cultural barrier to knowledge retention. The study revealed that the most important factors that relate to knowledge management and career development – promotion and professional specialisation – are the most affected. The study concluded that IT professionals are a critical factor that can impact knowledge management and the development of an employee's career efforts.

Given the series of findings in previous empirical research some of which are enumerated above, this study hypothesises as follows:

H₀₁: There is no relationship between employee career counselling and employee job satisfaction in Palmera Microfinance Bank, Uromi.

H₀₂: There is no positive relationship between employee training programmes and employee job satisfaction in Palmera Microfinance Bank, Uromi.

H₀₃: There is no relationship between employee career mentoring and employee job satisfaction in Palmera Microfinance Bank, Uromi.

Employee Job Satisfaction and Organisational Performance

Research on employee job satisfaction and organisational performance abound in literature. Some previous research has found positive relationship between Job satisfaction and organisational performance. For example, Grant et al. (2010), using a research survey, investigated the satisfaction level of a sample of bank tellers at a particular large Bank and found that the bank tellers were very dissatisfied with their jobs stating that they were "just glorified clerks" and that their jobs were boring and felt micromanaged because they were unable to make even the smallest decisions. By re-designing and altering their job schedules, the bank tellers job satisfaction increased in no time. A survey was taken six months later and it was found that not only were the tellers more satisfied with their role but they were also more committed to the organisation. The study indicated that there was an increase in performance by the tellers and that the job satisfaction arising from the job redesign had positive effects that lasted at least four years (Grant et al., 2010).

In a study of the Canadian credit Union by Alidou and André (2013), it was confirmed that there is a positive link between job satisfaction and employee performance. The study suggests that training and information influence the job satisfaction of employees as well as their autonomy, knowledge and judgment in exercise of their duties and functions. The study also confirmed that the determinants of

job satisfaction as presented in Human Resource (HR) literature are appropriate and indeed have an influence on job performance (Alidou& André, 2013).

Also, there was a study by Muhammad et al., (2021) that investigated the relationship between five factors of job satisfaction and organisational performance in Pakistan's Banking sector. Using the structural and measurement models, the study's findings were mixed. On one hand, payment (salary) and promotion were found not to have any relationship with organisational performance. However, on the other hand, supervision, fringe benefits, and contingent rewards (proxy for job satisfaction) were found to positively correlate with organisational performance.

Furthermore, Sadiq et al. (2020), using the exploratory survey research design, investigated 100 employees of W.E. Apparel, a firm in Pakistan using a random sampling method. The study found that there is an existing relationship between organisational performance and the level of job satisfaction. Specifically, the study found a significant relationship between work satisfaction and organisational performance. From the foregoing, it was hypothesised that:

H₀₄: There is no positive relationship between employees' job satisfaction and performance of Palmera Microfinance Bank, Uromi.

Research Methodology

Primary data source was used in this study as the research design was survey. One microfinance Bank – Palmera Microfinance Bank Limited, Uromi – was surveyed with the total staff strength of 58. The entire 58 members were used as our sample given that it is small and will enable us to draw generalisation without any sample error term (Saunders et al, 2007). A total of 58 copies of structured questionnaire were distributed to all 58 members of staff. The instrument was based on the 5-Likert rating scale of strongly agreed (SA) rated 5, agreed (A) rated 4, undecided (UD) rated 3, disagreed (D) rated 2 and strongly disagreed (SD) rated 1. The survey instrument was validated and also tested for reliability scoring a Cronbach's alpha of 0.68. A Spearman's correlation was conducted to test our hypotheses at 5% significance level utilising the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 25.

Presentation and Analysis of Data

Table 1 summarises the analysis of the characteristics of the 58 respondents of Palmera Microfinance Bank, Uromi.

Table 1: Demographic Profile of Respondents

Description	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Gender of Respondents		
Male	41	70.7
Female	17	29.3
Marital Status		
Married	23	39.7
Single	35	60.3
Age		
Below 30yrs	25	43.1
30-35yrs	16	27.6
36-40yrs	11	19.0
Above 40yrs	6	10.3

Educational Qualification		
SSCE	8	13.8
OND	10	17.2
BSc/HND	25	43.1
Master/PhD	15	25.9
Years of experiences		
0-5years	8	13.8
6-10years	15	25.9
11-15years	17	29.3
16-20years	10	17.2
21-30 years	8	13.8

Table 1 summarises the characteristics of respondents of Palmera Microfinance Bank, limited. The table revealed that the Bank is male dominated with more than 70% as against their female counterparts. True to type, there are more unmarried staff members of the bank than those married. Young people dominate the bank with 52(89.7%) of them below 40 years of age. As a bank seriously competing with more than 6 commercial banks within the area, majority of the staff members (40 i.e. 69%) hold the Bachelor’s degrees in various disciplines. 25 of the respondents hold either the HND or University degrees while 15 hold the higher degrees at both the Master and PhD levels majority of whom are management team. Nearly all the respondents except for 8 of them have being with the Bank for more than 5 years. Some of the respondents are founder members of the Bank.

Test of Hypotheses

Four hypotheses were tested using the Pearson correlation statistical tool with the aid of SPSS version 25. The individual results of the test are represented in Tables 2 to 5. The hypotheses tested were first illustrated in section 1 and in literature review section. Appendix 1 is the descriptive stat while Appendix 2 illustrates a combined correlation matrix of all the 4tested hypotheses.

Discussion of Results

The objective of this study is to investigate the relationship between career development and employee job satisfaction as well as organisational performance. From Table 2, the result of the first hypothesis revealed that the coefficient of the relationship between career counselling (CACL) and employee job satisfaction (EMPJSAT) is positive given that $r = 0.713^{**}$ at $\alpha < 0.001$. Therefore, the null hypothesis is hereby rejected while the alternative hypothesis is accepted. This implies that there is a significantly positive relationship between career counselling and employee job satisfaction. This result supports the findings of Khan et al (2011).

Table 2: Result of the Test of Hypotheses 1

		CACL	EMPJSAT
Pearson	Career Counselling (CACL)	1	.713**
Correlation	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N		58

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (1-tailed).

The result of test of the second hypothesis in Table 3 shows that the Pearson Correlation (r) coefficient between career mentoring (CAMEN) and employee job satisfaction (EMPJSAT) in a one-tail test is 0.890** (see Appendix 2) at $\alpha < 0.001$ and 99% significance level. This shows that there is a very high positive relationship between career development and employee job satisfaction. Given this result, the

null hypothesis is rejected while the alternative hypothesis is accepted. This result corroborates the findings of Tumwesigye (2010). Thus, the study concludes that there is a significantly positive relationship between career mentoring and employee job satisfaction.

Table 3: Result of the Test of Hypotheses 2

		CAMEN	EMPJSAT
Pearson	Career Mentoring (CAMEN)	1	.890**
Correlation	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N		58

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (1-tailed).

Result of the third hypothesis depicted in Table 4 indicates that there exists a positive relationship between employee training (EMPT_r) and employee job satisfaction given that the Pearson correlation (r) coefficient $r = 0.606^{**}$ at $\alpha < 0.001$ and 99% significance level. Thus, we reject H_0 and accept H_A . This result corroborates the findings of Enyioko&Ikoro (2017) and Sobia et al (2013) in their independent separate findings.

Table 4: Result of the Test of Hypotheses 3

		EMPT _r	EMPJSAT
Pearson	Employee Training (EMPT _r)	1	.606**
Correlation	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N		58

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (1-tailed).

The result of the fourth and final hypothesis shown in Table 5 shows a significantly positive relationship between employee job satisfaction (EMPJSAT) and organisational performance (ORGP_{ERF}) given a Pearson correlation coefficient $r = 0.855^{**}$ at $\alpha < 0.001$ and 99% significance level. As a consequence, we reject H_0 and accept H_A . This result is in tandem with the findings of Agboola et al. (2020).

Table 5: Result of the Test of Hypotheses 4

		EMPJSAT	ORGP _{ERF}
Pearson	Employee Job Satisfaction (EMPJSAT)	1	.855**
Correlation	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N		58

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (1-tailed).

Conclusion

Finally, this study concludes that there are strong indications that a high positive relationship exists between career development as characterised in this study and employee job satisfaction and between employee job satisfaction and overall organisational performance in Palmera Microfinance limited, Uromi. This implies that either career development helps to improve the commitment of an employee as a result of the satisfaction he derives from the commitment of his organisation towards his career development or it is the other way round. Thus, beyond the above general assertion, this study is

presently unable to categorically state the causal relationship between career development and employee job satisfaction and between job satisfaction and organisational performance.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations are hereby proffered:

That the management of Palmera Microfinance Bank should stick to its present crop of employees who seemed motivated enough to be sentimentally attached to the ideals, mission and vision of the Bank. However, for those other firms who may have a different experience, this study would advice that they hire workers whose values and goals converge with those of the organisation. Employee and organisational commitments are said to be central to and predicated on the alignment or congruence of the values and goals of both the employees and employers.

That Palmera Microfinance Bank must continue with the high level of commitment it presently offers to its employees by upping its present level of career development strategies. The argument is that if employees are bothered and concerned about losing their jobs due mainly to noncommittal to their welfare/career development, there is the likelihood that their level of commitment would wane. In the same vein, if employees are not given adequate resources to work and they do not receive training to improve their skills and knowledge, they are likely to see such an organisation as not interested in or committed to their career development.

Finally, Palmera Microfinance Bank must continue to provide organisational level programmes – counselling, mentorship, and training – which offer a continuous guidance to employees on how to manage their respective careers and assist them in shaping their long-term career development objectives. Such organisational level initiatives have the tendency to motivate their employees making them feel valued and valuable and appreciated by the Bank. Without a doubt, such initiatives can completely stop or reduce the rate of staff turnover and help increase the level of job satisfaction among employees in Palmera Microfinance Bank limited. Commitment to employee welfare such as career development requires that employees discuss their short and long term career expectations with their organisation to enable such organisation develop measures that can assist the employees develop and nurture their own respective individual careers to their satisfaction.

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Appendix 1

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Career Counselling (CACL)	.7819	.4214	58
Career Mentoring (CAMEN)	.6997	.4677	58
Employee Training (EMPTTr)	.8348	.3816	58
Employee Job Satisfaction (JOBSAT)	.6457	.4857	58
Organisational Performance (ORGPFR)	.7176	.4599	58

Appendix 2

Table 3: Results of the Test of Hypotheses

			CAME		EMPJSA	ORGPFR	
			CACL	N	EMPTTr	T	F
Pearson Correlation	CACL	Correlation Coefficient	1.000				
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.				
	CAMEN	Correlation Coefficient	.801**	1.000			
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.			
	EMPTTr	Correlation Coefficient	.849**	.680**	1.000		
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.		
	EMPJSAT	Correlation Coefficient	.713**	.890**	.606**	1.000	
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.	
	ORGPFR	Correlation Coefficient	.835**	.960**	.709**	.855**	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).